

BOX MODULUS USING FULL COMPOSITE STRUCTURES : MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITE SLAB

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ABSTRACT

The study is part of the MOOVABAT project aimed at defining innovative technological buildings with low environmental impact and characterised by the capacity to constantly adapt with the changing of their users' needs. In this context, the mechanical performance of a fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) frame, chosen as structural solution for the composite slab, was investigated. Specifically, the research study aims at experimentally define the load displacement behaviour of composite slab. To this purpose two full scale composite slab were tested to evaluate the strength and the stiffness. The experimental results show that the strength of the connection is higher than that required to satisfy both Serviceability Limit State and Ultimate LS loading conditions. Moreover, it also provided an accurate solution to obtain a strong composite slab.

KEYWORDS

Composite structure, beam-to-column connection, pultruded fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP), portal frame joints, MOOVABAT project.

INTRODUCTION

This article summarizes the various advances concerning the design of a modular structure within the framework of the MOOVABAT project. Among the various construction principles envisaged by the LMC², the study is particularly focused on the all-composite solution. The structural use of fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) materials is an innovative solution that indeed seems to meet the specific needs of the MOOVABAT project. Health care laboratory and medical centre are often subjected to significant changes in their structure to meet new requirements due to a constant evolution of the users' needs [1]. These structural modifications may result in significant economic and environmental impact. In this context the MOOVABAT project, joining expertise of companies in the field of energy and construction, and research laboratories, was conceived with the aim of defining innovative technological building characterised by a low environmental impact, and by an adequate versatility to promptly respond to the demands of this dynamic and constantly evolving context. Composite material was select to achieve this objective. Typical GFRP profiles includes E-glass continuous filament mats or woven fabrics, providing transversal strength, and unidirectional fibre threads running along the pultrusion length, providing longitudinal strength and stiffness.

The two main advantages of this type of material are respectively their high strength/weight ratio and their excellent resistance to chemical attack. The use of modular building, generally requiring few weeks for both designing and construction, and easily adaptable to several configurations, emerged as a smart technical solution for this purpose [2, 3]. Several construction solutions, guaranteeing fast implementation, versatility in their application and satisfying mechanical properties, can be considered for the structure of modular buildings. The mechanical properties of FRP are not the same in all directions, because the manufacturing process (pultrusion) gives a privileged orientation to the fibers. These different specificities are taken into account in the provisional version of the Eurocodes for FRP which will be released in principle in 2020. The provisional document recommends taking into account safety factors (manufacturing, temperature, humidity, creep, fatigue) and proposes methods of calculations adapted for the phenomena of instability. As shown by certain research works, closed sections (tubular) perform better from a mechanical point of view than open sections (profile I). The proposed solution for the frame of the module structure is thus made up of rectangular section beams. These beams consist of U-sections assembled by gluing with thin plates. In order to ensure a certain

modularity, it is planned to assemble using metal connectors and by bolting the different structural elements of the module (beam, post, partition, slab) [4]. The construction system envisaged is shown in Figure 1.

It is important to emphasize that in any case, exclusively glued assemblies are not recommended in most calculation guides due to the lack of standards and feedback on the subject (example: Fiberline dimensioning manual). For partitions and slabs, the idea is to use the WallE+system. Wall E+ is a new patented circular GFRP material, designed to simplify all stages of construction while exceeding environmental expectations. A first experimental stage has already made it possible to validate the use of these thin hollow girder according to the specifications. This brand new construction system makes it possible to encapsulate the insulating material and allows the passage of fluid and electricity networks. The all-composite solution makes it possible to have a relatively light structure which therefore makes it possible to limit the oversizing of the metal structure on which the pods will rest. However, it seems interesting from a mechanical point of view but also to improve the durability of the slab, to pour a concrete slab in the upper part of the WallE+.

These studies, combined with numerical applications, emphasised the importance of an accurate definition of the bending stiffness and strength [5, 6]. It was also highlighted the need of comparing the mechanical performance of FRP structural elements with serviceability and ultimate limit states to show the suitability of the material for designing purposes [7, 8]. In this context, the present study aims at investigating the mechanical performance of GFRP slab. Specifically, the load displacement behaviour. The results show that system is largely capable of withstanding the required loading configurations to satisfy both SLS and ULS conditions. However, by showing a shear failure located nearby the support. The paper includes a first part in which the MOOVABAT prototype is described, and a preliminary structural analysis is conducted to define the magnitude of the expected actions. Then, the material adopted, with specific attention to the bending behaviour. The results are presented and discussed.

Figure 1: 3D representation of the MOOVABAT modular element

In addition, different configurations can be encountered given the modular nature of the pods. The various possible configurations are illustrated in Figure 4. Configuration 1 is the most unfavorable because the absence of partitions on the two side faces of the module accentuates the deflection and the level of stress on the beam L. In Figure 2, the transverse beam (T), longitudinal beam (L) and column (P) form the structural framework of the modules. These elements play a bracing role.

Figure 2: Different modular construction needed

MATERIALS DESIGN AND METHODS

Materials

Pultruded GFRP structural members used as beam and column within the study are characterised by a closed cross section (Fig. 3). The elements, obtained by embedding glass-fibres in polyester matrix, were provided by the company TopGlass [9], and they are labelled as TRIGLASS® profiles. The section was created by assembling U profiles constituting the bottom and the top part (60 mm high, 200 mm wide and 10 mm thick) and flat profiles placed on the sides (30.8 mm wide and 7 mm thick). The elements were assembled by using a polyurethane adhesive, with the commercial name of ADEKIT® H6236 [10], after having accurately prepared the joining surfaces with isopropanol. The adhesively bonded connection is characterised by a delamination strength of 8 MPa assessed in accordance with the EN ISO 10365 standard [11]. For the composite slab Wall-E profile made of GFRP are used [12].

Figure 3: wall-E description

Main mechanical of pultruded GFRP members, provided by the manufacturer, are listed in Table 1 together with the reference standard adopted for the characterisation. Properties concern both longitudinal and transversal directions.

Table 1: Main mechanical properties of pultruded GFRP elements.

Properties	Longitudinal	Transversal	Reference standard
Tensile strength	400 MPa	30 MPa	ASTM D638
Tensile modulus of elasticity	26 GPa	8 GPa	
Compressive strength	220 MPa	70 MPa	ASTMD695
Compressive modulus of elasticity	18 GPa	7 GPa	
Shear strength	30 MPa	-	ASTM D2344
Shear modulus of elasticity	3 GPa	-	EN 13706
Poisson's ratio	0.28	0.12	ASTM D3039

Joints were implemented by means of steel plates fastened to the pultruded GFRP members by means of self-drilling screws. This solution was preferred to others, i.e. GFRP plate-to-plate, riveted or bonded connections, for its suitability to be easily either implemented or disassembled in view of applications in modular structures as MOOVABAT ones. Metallic plates have a thickness of 6.2 mm, so to behave as a rigid element uniformly distributing stresses among the screws.

Design

Table 2 summarizes the different loads that were considered in the calculations. The dead loads in Table 2 are also those that were used to estimate the weight of the module. The weight of the ventilation equipment is converted into a surface load of 15 daN/m². The specifications also require that the total weight of the module be less than 7 tons once equipped.

Table 1 : Loads applied on horizontal composite slab

Dead load :		
- Wall E+ (24 cm)		0.19 kN/ml
- Bonded beams (U200 + plates de 7 mm)		0.19 kN/ml
- concrete slab		15 kN
- Ventilation		0.15 kN/m ²
- plaster		0.09 kN/m ²
- steel connector		2.50 kN
Live loads :		
- Laboratory conditions		5.00 kN/m ²
- office		2.50 kN/m ²
Snow		0.56 kN/m ²
wind		0.53 kN/m ²

The composite slab is made of Wall-E system connected together and link to main support beams mechanically. To increase the stiffness of the ground slab concrete slab with a concrete strength of 40 MPa is used with a thickness layer of 4 cm.

The slab corresponds to a section with a width of 1.2m (i.e. two WallE+ unit boxes), of a slab of similar dimensions to the slab installed in the pod at scale 1. Consequently, the total length is 2.98m, i.e. the overall ribs of the pod. The fixing system between the side beams and the WallE+ boxes is made up of metal brackets in 6.2 mm thick galvanized steel. The connection between the brackets and the WallE+ boxes is ensured by means of 4 M6 diameter bolts. The connection between the WallE+ casings and the side beams is ensured by 4 TH self-drilling screws with a diameter of 6.3mm x 38mm (Figure 7).

Figure 4 : Connection details of WallE+ lateral beam

Table 3 : geometrical properties of the beam and composite slab

Beams U20cm×6cm×1cm plate 30,8cm×0,7cm		Top slab Walle+ (24 cm)		Gound slab Walle+ (24 cm) + concrete slab t = 4 cm	
S	103,12 cm ²	S	97,99 cm ²	S	330,80 cm ²
ly	17157,15 cm ⁴	ly	13340,69 cm ⁴	ly	27429,41 cm ⁴
lz	7756,85 cm ⁴	lz	47801,28 cm ⁴	lz	113791,63 cm ⁴
lx	15282,82 cm ⁴	lx	26488,54 cm ⁴	lx	
Wely	1035,38 cm ³	Wely	780,97 cm ³	Wely	1020,08 cm ³
Welz	724,94 cm ³	Welz	1593,38 cm ³	Welz	3793,05 cm ³
Av	43,12 cm ²	Av	23,99 cm ²	Av	

In serviceability condition, the modules rest on linear supports at the level of the lower L beams. The structure is modeled in Robot Structural Analysis. The theoretical calculation of the deflection at mid-span of the Walle+ elements is presented in table 5. The deflection is determined for a length of 2.5 m or 6 m. It is in fact possible to arrange the Walle+ either lengthwise (6 m) or widthwise (2.5 m). This study also shows the advantage of pouring a 4 cm concrete slab in the upper part of the Walle+. In Table 5, the results are in green when the deflection is low enough and in red when the deflection is greater than $L/500$. The orientation of the Walle+ in the direction of the width makes it possible to limit the deformation of the slab which takes up the operating load of 500 kg/m^2 . When the 24 cm Walle+ are arranged lengthwise, the deflection conditions ($L/500$) are verified only in the presence of a compression slab (concrete thickness 4 cm).

Figure 5: Bending moment distribution in the module and vertical displacement

Test configurations and procedures

The horizontal load was applied by means of a hydraulic press with maximum load capacity of 500 kN and a stroke of 100 mm. The loading system is supported by a reaction wall guarantying the imposed load to be properly transferred to the tested structure.

Figure 6: View of the specimen tested: a) beam-to-column; b) portal frame

In both the systems a horizontal load was vertically applied on the top of wall-E composite beams. The composite slab was tested in static loading conditions with a displacement control speed of 1 mm/min. The test set-up concerning the composite elements is represented in Figure 5. The connection, as well as the pultruded element section, are reproduced in full scale.

Two Linear Variable Displacement Transducers (LVDT) were placed on the slab to monitor the vertical displacement of the members at mid span and near the support. These displacements values were adopted to have an approximated estimation of the slab rotation during the test.

Figure 7: Test set-up of beam-to-column element (specimens T1 and T2_W) (measures in mm)

Two transducers (LVDT_1 and LVDT_2) were placed on the beams to monitor their vertical displacements during the test. Three strain gauges (SG_1, SG_2 and SG_3) were placed on the flange of the composite slab at different heights in order to have the strain distribution along the member length during the test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mechanical response of composite slab elements subjected to a vertical force applied on the horizontal member is presented as first in terms of load and horizontal displacement curve.

Fig. 8 shows load-displacement curves concerning the two composite slab system. The WallE+ elements are thin boxes, i.e. 4.5 mm for the core and 5.5 mm for the sole. WallE+ elements 2.5 m long were therefore tested in 3-point bending, the results are presented in Figure 10. The experimental results show that it is possible to double the breaking strength of the elements by casting a slab 4 cm concrete in the upper part of the WallE+. The flexural strength of the WallE+ elements is in fact 39.2 kN without concrete and 75.6 kN with a concrete slab. The tests showed failure by crushing and local buckling of the web at the level of the compression flange. In the presence of concrete, the failure mode is not the same. In the compressed part, shear failure and buckling of the web and flange are observed, but also transverse cracking of the concrete slab. In the case of standard size WallE+ (24 cm) the deflection limit is satisfied, however localized damage occurs for a load of approximately 11.25 kN. Finally, the tests clearly show that the resistance of the caissons depends above all on the phenomena of instability which lead to premature rupture, which occurs before reaching the maximum stress of the material. The presence of concrete, however, makes it possible to delay this type of disorder.

An elastic behaviour response is obtain which is obvious with such material but since the full system is tested with the connection system, it is possible to conclude that the connected Wall-E profile to the main beam is perfect without any sliding effect in the first elastic stage.

For higher load values, the loss of frictional capacity due to a slippage between the steel plate and GFRP members resulted in a small displacement increase up to a load value of about 30 kN for the slab without concrete and 50 kN for the slab with concrete. For higher load values, in the third phase, the displacement was increase suddenly to failure. This result emphasises that the sudden increase of displacement after local crushing of GFRP.

The results can be easily compared with a simplified numerical model reproducing the tested element. This representation, typically adopted for similar systems [13], allows to describe the mechanical response of the system regardless of the adopted geometry, and so to verify that results are in line with standard criteria [14].

The failure occur by main GFRP bonded beam crushing on the top to over local stress. (Figure 09).

Figure. 8: Load-displacement curve

The resulted behaviour may be considered as the theoretical behaviour of the connection, in linear conditions, and with a rigid joint.

In figure 8, the secondary axis proposes to convert the force (KN) into an equivalent distributed load (KN/m²). Thus, the operating load $Q = 500 \text{ kg/m}^2$ induces a displacement of 1.25 mm and 1.6 mm, with and without concrete slab respectively. These values are slightly higher than the theoretical values. The service limit conditions are also satisfied ($\delta < L/500$). For orientation in the width direction, the thickness of the Walle+ elements could be optimized while remaining sufficiently thermally resistant (Walle+ 20 cm thick). For mineral wool type insulation ($\lambda = 0.035 \text{ W/mK}$), the thermal resistance of Walle+ elements is in fact 6.85 m²K/W for a standard Walle+ and 5.71 m²K/W for a 20 cm Walle+ thick.

Figure 09: Local failure of composite slab

CONCLUSIONS

The study presents the results of an experimental study aimed at investigating the mechanical behaviour of GFRP composite slab including steel plate fastened joints. The main outcomes of the research are reported as follow:

- The maximum capacity of the composite slab is much higher than the expected values from structural analysis. This aspect emphasises that the structure, mainly designed to guarantee practical logistic aspects related to the geometry of the prefabricated elements adopted in the modular prototype, is structurally oversized.
- composite slab specimens are characterised by a semirigid behaviour exhibiting a failure mode characterised by the local failure in the support area.
- GFRP slab vertically loaded exhibits a mechanical response characterised by an elastic phase and a failure of the most stressed joints, consistently with the behaviour showed by the beam-to-slab elements.
- The use of screw and bolts allows to get a semi rigid connection;

All in all, the study shows that GFRP prefabricated elements represent a valuable technical solution for the implementation of modular prototypes, capable of exhibiting sufficient structural strength. The proposed connecting system, a practical system suitable for installation and disassembly processes, provide a semi-rigid behaviour of the joint with a concentration of the damage in the connecting elements. However, the experimental results also emphasises that the exhibited capacity is much higher than the required strength, showing that there is still open for improvement to optimise the size of the connecting system in order to reduce oversizing issues. The simplified numerical model proposed in the study can be adopted as a tool to achieve such improvement.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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